

Towards understanding the adhesion increasing effect of sand in wheel-rail contacts

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Abstract. Sand in wheel-rail contacts is successfully used for a long time to increase adhesion. However, the physical effects responsible for this adhesion increase remain unclear. To improve the understanding of these effects an approach combining experiments with Discrete Element Method (DEM) modeling is followed. Results from initial breakage and high loading experiments on single sand grains under purely normal loading conditions show that the spreading behavior and the forming of clusters of solidified sand fragments depend on the type of sand and the contact conditions, namely dry and wet. The experimental data were used to develop, calibrate and validate DEM models including particle breakage. These DEM models can describe the observed effects. Finally, a systematic classification is presented where tangential relative motion due to slip can occur in a sanded wheel-rail contact. This is seen as an important basis for future experimental and modelling work.

Keywords: wheel-rail contact, sanding, low adhesion, testing, DEM

1 Introduction

Sanding systems are used to increase friction in the wheel-rail interface under low adhesion conditions caused, for example, by leaves or the “wet-rail phenomenon” [1]. Fig. 1 shows results from friction experiments on a High-Pressure-Torsion (HPT) test rig [2]. The tests have been carried out under dry and wet contact conditions and with two types of rail sand, typical rail sands from Great Britain (GB) and Austria (AT). The curves for the unsanded case are also shown as reference. As expected, in the unsanded case the measured Adhesion Coefficient (AC) is considerably lower under wet conditions compared to dry conditions. Under wet conditions, both types of sand show higher AC values compared to the unsanded case, also as expected. Interestingly, the GB sand shows higher values than the AT sand. Under dry conditions, the GB sand gives more or less the same AC values as the unsanded case. The AT sand shows lower AC values as the unsanded case under this condition. In summary, these exemplary results show that sand works as it should under wet conditions. However, the type of sand obviously has an influence on the results.

Wheel–rail sanding is a field of active research, where the adhesion increasing aspect is extensively investigated, a good overview is given in [3]. Although the positive effect of sand is proven, the underlying physical effects regarding the interaction of sand grains with wheel-rail surfaces and other contaminants are still not fully understood. In an on-going project, these phenomena are now investigated in detail. Experimental investigations were carried out at The University of Sheffield and the results were used to develop, calibrate and validate Discrete Element Method (DEM) models [4] at Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH. Such DEM models allow for the consideration of local effects within the contact region introduced by the sand particles and their fragments. The combination of such DEM models with the information from the experiments is believed to be the right approach to improve the understanding of sanded wheel-rail contacts.

Fig. 1. Adhesion coefficient measured on a HPT test rig under (a) dry and (b) wet conditions for the unsanded case, GB and AT sand. For more details see [2].

It is known that sand particles reaching the wheel-rail contact get crushed. After the first crushing – several centimetres in front of the contact patch due to the narrowing gap between wheel and rail – some of the resulting fragments are expelled from the running band, while others stay inside and get crushed again. Finally, some of them reach the contact. Under certain conditions, clusters of highly compacted sand powder can form which then interact with the wheel-rail surfaces and positively affect adhesion under slip conditions (shearing).

In this project, an attempt has been made to separate the relevant effects occurring in sanded wheel-rail contacts into two main stages: (1) behaviour of sand grains under purely normal loading and the impact of sand grains on wheel and rail surface roughness and (2) behaviour of sand under combined normal/tangential loading conditions. Parallel to the testing, DEM models were developed, calibrated and validated based on the experimental data.

In this paper, experimental results and initial DEM simulation results belonging to stage (1) are presented. Furthermore, a systematic classification regarding locations

where tangential relative motion due to slip can occur is proposed, belonging to stage (2). This is seen as an important basis for future experiments and modelling, leading to better understanding of the friction-enhancing phenomena.

2 Testing under purely normal loading

Two test series have been conducted at The University of Sheffield under purely normal loading conditions with the GB and the AT sands mentioned above (same as in Fig. 1). Single sand grains were crushed between two steel plates. Photos were taken pre and post testing. In the first test series, the initial breakage was investigated. These tests provide information about the fragment spreading and breakage behavior of single sand grains. In the second test series, single sand grains were loaded up to realistic wheel-rail normal loading conditions causing repeated crushing. These tests provided information about the size and shape of eventually developing clusters of crushed sand powder. In the following two subsections the results of these tests are summarized, further details can be found in [5].

2.1 Initial breakage

Experiments were carried out on a Universal Mechanical Tester (UMT) machine to investigate the initial breakage behaviour. For GB sand, 21 tests were conducted under dry and 23 under wet conditions. For AT sand, it was 23 tests for dry and wet conditions each. The breakage forces were used to fit a Weibull statistics [6] describing the relationship between particle stress and breakage probability, see Fig. 2(a). Surprisingly, the two types of sand show very similar breakage behaviour even though their performance in the friction tests is different as shown in Fig. 1. It needs to be mentioned that the average diameter of the two types of sand is different, with GB 1.54 mm and AT 1.25 mm. That means that even though the stresses at breakage are very similar, the breakage forces differ significantly from each other. The fitted Weibull statistics are later used in the DEM model to describe the breakage behaviour of the two types of sand.

Using the photos taken after initial crushing, in a post-processing step the position and area of the fragments was determined. Fig. 2(b) and (c) show cumulative histograms for the two types of sand, where the fragment distance is weighted by its area divided by the sum of all fragments. The half-width of a conceptual wheel-rail running band is highlighted as a grey box. For GB sand, the contact condition made a big difference: under dry conditions 68% of the fragments' area stayed within the conceptual running band, while it was 98% under wet conditions. This influence of the contact condition is less pronounced for AT sand: Even under dry conditions 93% of the fragments' area stayed within the conceptual running band and under wet conditions it was 100%.

Fig. 2. Experimental results from initial breakage experiments with GB and AT sand: (a) fitted Weibull statistics, (b) and (c) distance weighted by area for GB and AT sand. The half-width of a conceptual wheel-rail running band is shaded in grey. For more details see [5].

2.2 Repeated breakage under realistic loading conditions

After investigating initial grain breakage, single sand grains were crushed between hardened steel plates under a realistic wheel-rail mean contact pressure of 900 MPa. This stress is considerably higher than e.g. in geotechnical applications. For both types of sand and for both dry and wet contact conditions, 5 tests were conducted. A non-contact imaging and measuring tool named Alicona InfiniteFocus SL was used to take high resolution 3D scans of the crushed grains. In these tests, a varying amount of fragments were expelled from the contact during repeated breakage. Nevertheless, in all cases clusters of solidified sand were formed. GB sand under dry conditions showed a high variation in the amount of material, which stayed within the contact area. Example results can be seen in Fig. 3 (top images). A typical result for AT sand under dry conditions can be seen in Fig. 4 (top images). This cluster has a side length of about 3 mm and showed a height up to 140 μm in the Alicona scan which is significantly larger than the observed clusters for the GB test result example.

Under wet conditions, both types of sand typically showed only one big cluster of solidified sand powder, see Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, bottom images. The cluster of GB sand has a side length of 4.4 mm and a height up to 220 μm . In contrast, the cluster of AT sand is much smaller with a side length of about 3 mm and heights up to 160 μm due to a smaller initial diameter of AT sand grains. Although hardened steel plates have been used in these experiments, the 3D scans show, that the developing clusters of sand fragments cause indentations on the surfaces due to plastic deformation (see Alicona scans in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.)

Fig. 3. Example results for high loading test of GB sand under dry and wet conditions. For more details see [5].

Fig. 4. Example results for high loading test of AT sand under dry and wet conditions. For more details see [5].

3 DEM simulations

Both types of normal loading experiments presented in section 2 were modelled using the DEM method [4], with some of the tests being used for model calibration and some for model validation. Here, only an overview about the modelling and the simulation results is presented, the detailed results are currently being published [7].

For particle shape representation in the developed DEM model spheres with rolling resistance were used. This approach is computationally efficient and can mimic the behavior of non-spherical particles, what the sand particles and their fragments obviously represent. For modelling the particle-particle and particle-wall contacts, the Hertz-Mindlin contact law including a viscous damping is used [8][9][10][11][12][13]. For modelling the forming of the observed clusters of sand fragments, cohesion was added to the Hertz-Mindlin contact law [14]. To consider the reduced spread of fragments under wet contact conditions, a drag force following Stokes' law was applied to each particle.

To account for particle breakage, the computationally efficient particle replacement method was used [15]. Information regarding the strength of the particles was taken from the Weibull statistics presented in Fig. 2(a). If the stress on a particle exceeds its strength, then it is replaced by fragments (20 spheres, see Fig. 5(a)). To avoid infinite breakage of particles, a minimal radius is introduced. Fig. 5(b) and (c) show exemplary results for GB sand under dry conditions. The developed DEM model is able to describe the spreading behavior of the fragments and the development of clusters of sand fragments.

Fig. 5. (a) particle breakage “replacement method”. Exemplary test and simulation results for GB sand under dry conditions, (b) initial breakage and (c) high loading conditions.

4 Classification where tangential relative motion can occur

The test results presented in section 2 show that individual sand grains passing through the wheel-rail contact form clusters of solidified sand fragments and cause surface indentations on wheel and rail surfaces due to plastic deformation (change of roughness). It is assumed that small individual sand fragments do not play an important role. The question now is how the clusters of sand fragments encapsulated between rough wheel and rail surfaces positively affect friction under shearing conditions. This leads to the question of where the tangential relative motion due to slip occurs. In [5] it was hypothesized, that the shearing behavior of the clusters of solidified sand powder is the dominating effect combined with form closure effects due to the indentation of these clusters into wheel and rail surfaces. The form closure effect would explain why larger particles often show a better performance compared to smaller particles under low adhesion conditions [16][17]. It is assumed that shear bands evolve within the clusters formed. However, this needs to be further investigated in detail both experimentally and virtually by using DEM models. What particularly needs to be better understood in this context is the shearing behavior of solidified sand fragments under high normal loading, which is why mini-shear box experiments are planned.

In order to be able to carry out the above-mentioned future investigations systematically, it makes sense to distinguish between the following two cases (see Fig. 6): (1) tangential relative motion occurs within a certain material and (2) relative motion occurs in an interface between two materials. In reality, it is very likely that a combination of both takes place. In Table 1, all possible configurations for the two cases shown in Fig. 6 are summarized.

In a next step of the project it is planned to systematically determine quantitative values for the material and interface properties summarized in Table 1 to be used as input for the DEM models, which are coefficient of friction values for the interfaces (dry and wet conditions) and shear force-displacement relationships for solidified sand fragments, leaf layers, etc. under varying normal loading conditions.

Table 1. Configurations where relative motion can occur within materials and interfaces.

Case	Interface	Material
without third body layer, Fig. 6(a)	steel-steel	steel
	steel-sand	sand
with third body layer (leaves), Fig. 6(b)	steel-steel	steel
	steel-sand	sand
	steel-leaves	leaves
	sand-leaves	

Fig. 6. Tangential relative motion in sanded contacts: (a) without third body layer and (b) with third body layer (leaves).

5 Conclusions

This study aims to provide a better understanding of the physical effects that are responsible for the adhesion increasing effect of sand in wheel-rail contacts. Therefore, an approach combining experiments with DEM modeling is followed. DEM modeling has been chosen because it allows local considerations within the contact patch where experimental observations are difficult. The following conclusions can be drawn:

- Initial breakage tests: the spreading behavior of the sand fragments after initial breakage – typically several centimeters in front of the contact – depends on the type of sand and contact conditions. Under wet conditions, more or less all the sand fragments remain within a typical wheel-rail running band.
- High normal loading tests: if the fragments are further loaded up to realistic wheel-rail contact loads, clusters of solidified sand fragments form which cause surface indentations due to plastic deformation (change of surface roughness). The number, size, and thickness of these clusters again depends on the type of sand and the contact conditions.
- A DEM model has been developed that is able to describe the observed behavior in the initial breakage and high loading tests. In this model, particle breakage is implemented by using the replacement method and cohesion is considered in the particle contact laws to account for the development of sand powder clusters.
- A systematic classification regarding the location where tangential relative motion due to slip can occur has been proposed. It is hypothesized, that relative motion mainly occurs within the formed sand powder clusters

(forming of shear bands) and that the shearing behavior of these clusters in combination with form closure effects, predominantly determines the effectiveness of a certain type of sand under wet conditions. However, this needs to be proven systematically and therefore the classification presented – distinguishing between relative motion in materials and interfaces – represents a good basis for the planning of future experiments under combined normal/tangential loading conditions as well as for the associated further development of the DEM models.

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